

PESTS OF VEGETABLE CROPS AND MEASURES TO CONTROL THEM (IN THE CASE OF ANDIJAN REGION)

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Abstract. *This article describes pests of vegetable crops and measures to combat them.*

Keywords: *eggs, larva, fungus, nymph, adults, tomato moth, aphid, spider mite, colorado potato beetle, saprophyte, hyphomycete, pathogen, alternaria, late blight, fusarium, tobacco mosaic, downy mildew, etc.*

Introduction. Geographical location and climatic conditions of Uzbekistan are one of the favorable regions for growing agricultural products.

Like other agricultural crops, vegetable cultivation areas in our country are expanding year by year.

Among the countries of Central Asia, Uzbekistan's fertile soil and climatic conditions allow high yields of vegetable crops in well-irrigated lands.

In recent years, like other branches of agriculture, vegetable growing has developed, and the area of crops is expanding in all regions of our republic. Andijan region is also one of the important regions in the cultivation of vegetable products.

In the cultivation of such vegetable products, it is important that they are ecologically clean, of high quality, and that they are protected from diseases and pests on time.

Vegetables are one of the most consumed types of crops and are rich in vitamins necessary for the human body.

The demand for vegetable products is increasing day by day not only in the domestic market, but also in foreign markets.

According to the data, the export of vegetables in our country in January-November 2023 increased by 23% to 54.2 thousand tons, and onions increased by 45.9% to 263.8 thousand tons in January-November 2023, respectively 40.9 million USD and 54.4 million worth of products were exported.

But in recent years, there are many cases of damage to vegetable crops by harmful organisms. Examples of these pests include tomato moth, aphid, spider, Colorado beetle, that lead to diseases such as alternaria, fusarium, phytophthora, powdery mildew, viral and other diseases.

One of the main reasons for this is their seed production, secondly, agrotechnical measures implemented during the vegetation period of the plant, and thirdly, it indicates that the measures of coordinated control against harmful organisms are not implemented on time.

This has a negative effect on the cultivation of biologically clean and high-quality products, and in the future, it leads not only to a decrease in the productivity of plants, but also to the production of low-quality products that do not meet the demand.

In order to prevent this, peasants - farmers, agroclusters, and owners of private estates must first of all carry out high-quality and timely agrotechnical activities in cultivated areas, timely detection of harmful organisms, and rational use of the combined protection system of the fight against harmful organisms.

Literature review. Tomato fusarium wilt (fusarium wilt) is caused by the *Fusarium oxysporum* f. *lycopersici* hyphomycete fungus, does not damage other crops except tomatoes. The fungal disease Fusarium wilt occurs in greenhouses and open fields. Damaged seeds, cotyledons and young shoots rot completely. Disease in heavy soils spreads very quickly. The fungus is a heat-loving organism and causes severe damage to plants at soil temperatures of 21-33°C, the optimum being 28°C. Excessive application of nitrogen fertilizers will aggravate the disease. The pathogen enters the plant tissues through its veins. (B. Khasanov 2008).

Tomato phytophthora is caused by the *Phytophthora infestans* oomycete fungus. In recent years, tomato phytophthora has become a common disease in greenhouses in Uzbekistan. (Isomiddinov, Rahmatov, 2007). In cool and damp (rainy, dewy) weather, 60-70 percent of tomato fruits can be damaged. (Ganiev, Nedorezkov, 2005).

The fungus overwinters in open fields on the soil in plant debris and weeds belonging to the sedge family. The disease also spreads from potatoes and tomatoes in fields adjacent to crops. (B. Khasanov 2008).

Since tomatoes are mainly eaten raw, it is very important that they do not contain pesticide residues (environmentally friendly). For this reason, it is recommended to protect crops from phytophthora as much as possible, without using fungicides, using the above-mentioned agrotechnical and preventive measures. (Pidoplichko, 1977a; Peresyppkin, 1982; Watterson, 1985; Vanekidr., 1989; Ganiev, Nedorezkov, 2005).

Tobacco mosaic of tomatoes is caused by the tobacco mosaic virus (TMV) (Nicotiana virus 1). In Uzbekistan, it is widely distributed in open ground and especially in greenhouses. The virus affects tomatoes, eggplants, peppers and many other crops. (B. Khasanov 2008).

The infection persists in plant debris and infects tomato seedlings planted the following year through their roots. In Uzbekistan, natural foci of **TMV** have been noted in the symbiont (*Sysymbrium loeselii*). Although not the primary source of infection, the virus has been shown to be transmitted to tomatoes by rodents (e.g., grasshoppers and beetles). (B. Khasanov 2008).

In field conditions, the virus spreads to tomatoes from weeds infected with mosaic (*Datura stramonium*, ituzum, wild tobacco, mustard, etc.). From season to season, the virus can also be transmitted through seeds, but mosaic mainly spreads during the collection and transplantation of seedlings in the field. With an early onset of the disease, yields can decrease by 10-15% in open ground and up to 50% in greenhouses. (Vlasov, 1958, 1960; Kuznetsova, Tursumetova, 1970; Vlasov, Larina, 1982; Peresyppkin, 1982; MacNa beatal., 1983; Watterson, 198; Tsyplenkov, 1986; Fletcher, 1987; Vyangelyauskaiteandetc., 1989; Sattarovaandb., 2003).

Alternaria leaf rot of sweet peppers is caused by the saprotrophic (weak parasite) hyphomycete fungus *Alternaria alternata* (and possibly *A. solani*). The pathogen enters the fruit through holes and various other wounds caused by insect bites. (B. Khasanov 2008).

Downy mildew on polis crops is caused by the oomycete fungus *Peronoplasmopara Cubensis* (synonym *Pseudoperonospora Cubensis*). All citrus crops are susceptible to the disease, but cucumbers and **melons** are most severely damaged. (B. Khasanov 2008).

There is little information in the literature about the spread of false powdery mildew in Uzbekistan (Liang, Khoshimkhodjaeva, 2007); Observations by employees of the Ministry of Education and Culture (Sh.T. Khodjaev) revealed that it is widespread in cucumbers grown in greenhouses in Fergana Valley.

Also, a lack of nitrogen, phosphorus, potassium, micro- and macroelements of manganese, calcium, magnesium, iron, zinc, sodium, chlorine, sulfur and other elements in mineral fertilizers has a negative impact on the growth and development of the plant.

As a result, the plant becomes sluggish, its immunity decreases, and susceptibility to diseases increases. (B. Khasanov 2008).

Tomato moth - (*Tuta absoluta* Meir) female butterflies lay eggs mainly under the leaves of the plant, on the tops and growth points, in some cases in the soil. In total, butterflies can lay 20-250 eggs. The eggs are laid mainly on the leaves (73%), the rest - on the fruits and stems located on the upper side of the plant. The hatched worms feed inside the leaf.

Tomato moth damages the plant throughout the growing season. The worm damages the buds, leaves, stems and fruits of the plant at the growth point, as well as the root canal at the bottom of the stem.

The tomato moth reproduces 5-7 times in the summer season, 3-4 times in winter in greenhouses, for a total of 8-11 times in a year. (Sh. Khodjaev 2019).

Cotton or melon aphid (*Aphis gossypii* Glove) overwinters as larvae and adults in weeds, mainly on plants such as button and wild mustard. Cotton sap overwinters in April and is first found in weeds. The aphid damages plants at the larval and adult stages. In early May, it flies to cotton and sorghum crops. In May-June and September-October, it flies and reproduces. The aphid is an omnivorous pest, damaging 46 plant species. (Sh. Khodzhaev 2019).

Spider mite (*Tetranychus urticae* Koch.) is an omnivorous pest that damages more than 200 plant species, including cotton, vegetables, sugar cane, legumes, peanuts and other crops.

It is spread by wind, cobwebs, work tools and other ways. The optimum temperature is 26-33 degrees, relative humidity of 55-60 percent is considered moderate. It gives birth 12-20 times a year. (Sh. Khodjaev 2019).

Natural pests - thrips eat eggs and larvae, adult lacewing larvae and storus beetles - spider mites (Sh. Khodjaev 2019).

Colorado potato beetle - (*Leptinotarsa decemlineata* Say) overwinters at a depth of 20-60 cm under field feeding conditions. In the spring, when the ground level warms up to 14-15 degrees, it flies out. It lays eggs under the leaves in groups of 12-80 pieces. On average, one beetle lays up to 400-700 eggs, sometimes up to 2400. Larvae and beetles mainly damage the leaves by eating them. Damages potatoes, eggplants, tomatoes and other crops. The Colorado potato beetle gives birth 1-3 times. (Sh. Khodjaev 2019).

Goals and objectives. It consists of monitoring the spread of harmful organisms of vegetable crops on the territory of the republic, determining the criteria for causing damage and developing coordinated measures to combat them. Vegetable crops planted in open and closed areas were taken as objects of observation.

Research materials and methods. In order to identify harmful organisms of vegetable crops, monitoring work was carried out on crops of tomatoes, sweet peppers and cucumbers planted in open and closed areas in Andijan region, Bulokboshi, Jalakuduk and Khodjaabad districts.

During the observation, samples were taken from infected tomato, sweet pepper and cucumber plants and examined in laboratory conditions.

M.K. Khokhryakov et al. (1969) and H.L. Barnett (1968) and N.M. Pidopalichko (1977) detectors were used to identify causative fungi.

In laboratory conditions, pathogenic fungi were isolated from infected plants on potato agar and artificial Chapek medium according to the method of S.F. Sidorova (1983). Harmful insects were identified according to V.V. Yakhontov (1962) and Sh. Khodjaev (2004).

Analysis and results. In crops of tomatoes, sweet peppers and cucumbers, monitoring was carried out in the greenhouses of OOO Davron Agro Sanoat, Tokhtasinboy Fruits in Jalalkuduk district, Zarnigor Obadlygi Gulshan, Yolbars in Khodjaabad district, Dilkushod Durdonasi, Polatjon, Azizbek Farm in Bulokbashi district located in Andijan region, and the following signs were found.

From the data in the table it is clear that the tomato plant is infected with the *Fusarium* wilt fungus. Among the samples of infected plants potato agar and artificial Chapek media *Fusarium spr.* fungi were isolated.

Table 1

Disease analysis of vegetable crops of Andijan region

No	Location of sampling	Variety	Field, ga	Disease symptoms	Disease and causative pathogens
1.	Andijan region, Buloqboshi district " Davron Agro Industry " LLC greenhouse	Tomato, Yusupov variety	0.7	The lower leaves of the tomato plant have turned yellow on one side and the plants have become pale. The withered leaves are drying up. The leaves are hanging on the branches without falling.	<i>Fusarium</i> wilt , <i>Fusarium oxysporum</i> f. <i>lycopersici</i>
2.	Bulokboshi district, "Tokhtasinboy fruits"	sweet pepper, Bulgaria – 79 variety	0.3	At the top of the fruit (where the flower is), the first symptoms like a scalding sensation appeared, then light brown, dry, papery spots appeared, and the top of the fruit was damaged.	<i>Alternaria</i> , <i>Alternaria solani</i> Sor .
3.	Bulokboshi district, "Tokhtasinboy fruits"	tomato, Lodge F1 variety	0.2	Leaf bands are bent downwards and leaves are falling, spots appear on the leaves that look like scalds from boiling water It has brown and dark-brown shriveled leaves, the leaf tissue is slightly pale and papery.	<i>Phytophthora</i> , <i>Phytophthora infestans</i> (<i>Mont.) de Bari</i>

4.	Andijan region, Jalalquduq district, "Zarnigor Obadlygi Gulshan "	Tomato, TMK - 22 variety	0.5	The lower leaves of the tomato plant have turned yellow on one side and the plants have become stunted. The withered leaves are drying up. Without falling leaves, they hang on the branches.	Fusarium wilt , <i>Fusarium oxysporum f. lycopersici</i>
5.	Andijan region, Jalakuduq district, "Yolbars" f/x	Tomato, TMK-22 variety	0.4	Leaf bands are bent downwards and leaves are drooping, spots appear on the leaves that look like scalds from boiling water It has brown and dark- brown shriveled leaves, the leaf tissue is slightly pale and papery.	Phytophthora , <i>Phytophthorai nfestans(Mont.) de Bari</i>
6.	Andijan region, Khojaabad district, the fam "Dilkushod durdonasi"	tomato, Madeira F1 variety	0.2	A common symptom on the leaves and fruits is <i>a mosaic</i> , a slight bulge on the leafdark-green and light- green parts of leaves are located one after the othertwisted and out of shape.	Tobacco mosaic, (<i>TMV</i>) <i>Nicotiana virus1</i>
7.	Andijan region, Khojaabad district, the farm "Polatjan", greenhouse	Cucumber, Majestic variety	0.3	Yellow and brown spots appeared on the leaves. Affected leaves begin to harden and dry out.	False flour dew, <i>Peronoplasmo para cubensis</i>
8.	Andijan region, Khojaabad district, the field "Azizbek", greenhouse	Cucumber, Crispina G 1 variety	0.2	Yellow and brown spots appeared on the leaves. Affected leaves begin to harden and dry out.	False flour dew, <i>Pseudoperonos poracubensis (Berk . et Curtis) Ro .</i>

Similarly, phytophthora in tomatoes of the varieties "TMK-22", "Lodzhein G' 1", the "Tobacco mosaic" virus in the variety "Madera F1", alternaria in sweet pepper of the variety "Bulgar-79", false flour in cucumber variety "Majestic" and "Crispina G1" are affected by dew diseases.

Plant infected with fusarium

An eggplant plant infected with fusarium

Sweet pepper fruit infected w

A tomato plant infected with phytophthora

A tomato plant infected with a viral disease

Tomato fruits infected with a virus disease

Cucumber plant infected with False flour dew disease

Cucumber plant infected with False flour dew disease

In the process of monitoring, tomato was partially damaged by tomato moth - (*Tuta absoluta* Meir) , aphid - (*Aphis gossypii* Glov) , cucumber spider mite - (*Tetranychus urticae* Koch) and Colorado potato beetle (*Leptinotarsa decemlineata* Say).

Tomato fruit infested by tomato moth

Tomato plant infested with aphids

An eggplant plant infested by the Colorado potato beetle

Spider mite infested cucumber plant

Appropriate recommendations were given to farmers regarding the harmful organisms detected during monitoring processes.

Summary

As a final conclusion, it is worth saying that based on the above considerations, in order to keep any types of crops within the criteria of economic damage of harmful organisms, it is necessary to carry out agrotechnical measures on time and in good quality (*selection of land, rotation of crops, fertilization , cultivation of seedlings , planting of land preparation , duration, thickness and scheme, care, watering, etc.)* that ensures timely and qualitative implementation of measures of coordinated control against harmful organisms.

As a result of this, the quality of the harvested crop improves, the gross yield increases, and the economic efficiency increases.

Recommendations

1. To give importance to agrotechnical measures in the cultivation of vegetable crops, i.e. crop rotation, fertilizing, growing seedlings, preparing the land for planting, planting period, thickness and scheme, maintenance, watering and other technological processes;

2. In the field, it is not recommended to plant vegetables and potatoes belonging to the same family (tomatoes, eggplants, sweet peppers, potatoes, etc.) and one type of vegetable and potato crops for several years consequently (tomatoes next year after tomatoes or potatoes after potatoes);

3. In a Fusarium disease during the growth period of the plant spraying with a base drug "Pseudomonas putida Pp-1" is recommended;

4. It is recommended to use azoxystrobin + difenoconazole, mancozeb + tricyclazole, propamocarb hydrochloride, based on chlorothalonil against alternaria, metalaxyl, mancozeb + mefenoxam, mancozeb + metalaxyl M, dimethomorph chlorothalonil + based on folpet, benomyl, penconazole, cymoxanil + mancozeb-based preparations against downy mildew.

5. If a plant infected with a viral disease is found during field treatment, the tools and equipment should be disinfected, the heavily infected plant should be uprooted and burned outside the field. Also, take measures to combat insects that spread the virus;

6. To control the spread of tomato moth, it is recommended to use pheromone traps. This method is of great importance for determining the spread and development of pests in nature and, as a result, for recommending biological or chemical measures to combat them;

7. When the economic damage criteria increases, it is recommended to use preparations based on acetamiprid, imidacloprid, emamectin benzoate against tomato moth, cyantraniliprole, diafenthuron based on aphids, indoxacarb + abamectin on spider mites, acetamiprid, alphacypermethrin, imidacloprid + lambda-cyhalothrin against Colorado beetle.

The use of any chemical means should be stopped 30 days before harvesting.

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